

1 **Phylogeography of a gypsum endemic plant across its entire distribution**
2 **range in the western Mediterranean**

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16 Running head: Phylogeography of a gypsum endemic plant

17 **ABSTRACT**

18 Premise of the study: Gypsum soils in the Mediterranean Basin house large numbers of edaphic
19 specialists that are adapted to stressful environments. The evolutionary history and standing
20 genetic variation of these taxa have been influenced by the geological and paleoclimatic
21 complexity of this area and the long-standing effect of human activities. However, little is
22 known about the origin of Mediterranean gypsophiles and the factors affecting their genetic
23 diversity and population structure.

24 Methods: Using phylogenetic and phylogeographic approaches based on microsatellites and
25 sequence data from nuclear and chloroplast regions, we evaluated the divergence time, genetic
26 diversity and population structure of 27 different populations of the widespread Iberian
27 gypsophile *Lepidium subulatum* throughout its entire geographic range.

28 Results: *Lepidium subulatum* diverged from its nearest relatives ~3 Mya, and the ITS and
29 *psbA/matK* trees supported the monophyly of the species. These results suggest that both
30 geological and climatic changes that occurred in the region around the Plio-Pleistocene
31 promoted its origin, compared to other evolutionary processes. We found high genetic diversity
32 in both nuclear and chloroplast markers, but a greater population structure in the chloroplast
33 data. This suggests that while seed dispersal is limited, pollen flow may be favored by the
34 presence of numerous habitat patches that enhance the movement of pollinators.

35 Conclusions: Despite being an edaphic endemic, *L. subulatum* possesses high genetic diversity
36 probably related to its relatively old age and high population sizes across its range, and
37 highlights the value of using different markers to fully understand the phylogeographic history
38 of plant species.

39 **Keywords:** Phylogeography, gypsophiles, genetic diversity, population structure, nuclear
40 microsatellites, cpDNA, pollen flow, seed dispersal, *Lepidium subulatum*

41 INTRODUCTION

42 The genetic diversity of plant populations and how it is distributed geographically across
43 species ranges depends on processes that operate at different spatial and temporal scales. The
44 Mediterranean Basin has experienced a highly complex geological and paleoclimatic history.
45 Past changes in its geological, climatic and ecological conditions, especially during the Pliocene
46 and Pleistocene (5.33-0.01 Mya), have been decisive in shaping the genetic composition of
47 Mediterranean plants (Blondel et al., 2010; Nieto Feliner, 2014). More recently, humans have
48 profoundly transformed Mediterranean ecosystems through long-standing, yet dynamic
49 activities (Blondel et al., 2010; Nieto Feliner, 2014), further contributing to modulate the
50 genetic diversity and structure of plant populations in this region (Thompson, 2005).

51 A particular example within Mediterranean taxa are gypsophiles, defined as plants that
52 are restricted to gypsum (calcium sulfate dihydrate) soils (Meyer, 1986). In the Mediterranean
53 Basin, these soils harbor rich plant communities with large proportions of endemic species
54 adapted to arid and semiarid conditions (Escudero et al., 2015). Iberian gypsum outcrops have
55 been dated to as old as the Cambrian, but more than two thirds of the gypsum soils in this area
56 appeared in the Cenozoic, mostly during the Neogene (Escavy et al., 2012). Different events
57 that occurred in this period favored the formation of gypsum outcrops. First, geological events
58 like the Alpine Orogeny allowed the accumulation of salts and sediments in basins (Escavy et
59 al., 2012). Furthermore, the tectonic uplift of the Gibraltar arc reduced water flow from the
60 Atlantic Ocean to the Mediterranean Sea, resulting in the Messinian Salinity Crisis (~6 - 5.3
61 Mya). This, together with global changes in sea level, produced the desiccation of the
62 Mediterranean Sea by evaporation processes that favored gypsum precipitation (Garcia-
63 Castellanos and Villaseñor, 2011). Second, changes in the paleoclimatic conditions of the
64 Mediterranean region further accelerated evaporation by rainfall reduction and prevented the
65 loss of precipitated gypsum by leaching (Parsons, 1976). The progressive aridification and

66 seasonality of precipitation that started 9.5-8 Mya (van Dam, 2006) led to the appearance of the
67 Mediterranean climate 3.2 Mya, characterized by high seasonality and marked summer drought
68 (Suc, 1984). Although both the availability of gypsum soils and the increasingly drier climatic
69 conditions of the late Miocene and Pliocene likely determined the origin of Iberian gypsophiles,
70 it is yet not established whether these species originated in gypsum environments or,
71 alternatively, in other stressful habitats from which they colonized gypsum soils (Escudero et
72 al., 2015).

73 A remarkable feature of gypsum environments is their discontinuous spatial
74 configuration. Not only are gypsum soils naturally fragmented into island-like outcrops
75 surrounded by other substrates (Escudero et al., 2015), but also anthropogenic practices like
76 agriculture and livestock grazing have exacerbated the natural patchiness of these habitats in
77 the Mediterranean region for centuries (Pueyo et al., 2008). Both natural and human-induced
78 fragmentation may affect the genetic diversity and structure of gypsophile populations due to
79 neutral processes such as genetic drift, demographic changes, inbreeding and reduced gene flow
80 (Aguilar et al., 2008). This unique spatial configuration may be even more critical in species
81 that lack effective seed dispersal mechanisms, as is the case in most widely-distributed
82 gypsophiles (Escudero et al., 2015). However, livestock practices like transhumance and
83 grazing could enhance gene flow between populations if they promote seed movement (Pueyo
84 et al., 2008; Azcárate et al., 2013). Consequently, genetic diversity and population structure of
85 gypsophiles may be determined by a complex interaction between landscape configuration and
86 land use, among others.

87 Phylogeography provides a useful framework to assess the origin and evolutionary
88 history of species and closely related species groups (Avice, 2000). Combining markers with
89 different mutation rates enables phylogeographic studies to elucidate how past and present
90 processes have modulated the genetic diversity and structure of populations (Wang, 2011).

91 Furthermore, the use of markers with different modes of transmission such as chloroplast DNA
92 (maternally inherited and dispersed only by seeds in most angiosperms) and nuclear DNA
93 (biparentally inherited and dispersed by both seeds and pollen) allows for the quantification of
94 the relative contribution of seed and pollen flow to the genetic structure of populations (Ennos
95 et al., 1999; Petit et al., 2005).

96 In this study, we used a phylogeographic approach based on nuclear microsatellite loci
97 and chloroplast and nuclear sequence data to assess the origin, genetic diversity and population
98 structure of the gypsophile *Lepidium subulatum* L. (Brassicaceae) throughout its entire
99 distribution range. *Lepidium subulatum* is a regionally dominant gypsophile endemic to the
100 Iberian Peninsula and North Africa and is the most geographically widespread gypsophile in
101 the western Mediterranean (Romão and Escudero, 2005). Because of its high substrate
102 specificity, dominance and life-history traits common to other gypsophiles, *L. subulatum*
103 provides a compelling study system to evaluate the genetic diversity, structure and date of origin
104 of gypsophiles. We studied 27 different populations that represent the current geographical and
105 climatic distribution of the species, to address the following questions: 1) When did the
106 evolutionary divergence of *L. subulatum* occur and how was it influenced by the complex
107 geological and paleoclimatic history of the Mediterranean Basin? 2) Do populations of the
108 species show different levels of genetic diversity? 3) Are populations genetically structured,
109 and if so, is this structure explained by their geographical location and/or by historic
110 demographic changes? and 4) Is genetic variation and population structure inferred by either
111 microsatellites or chloroplast markers different, and if so, how does it relate to pollen and seed
112 flow? This is the first study to estimate the date of origin of this species and the distribution of
113 genetic diversity across its entire geographical and climatic range. We expect that the complex
114 historical events experienced by Mediterranean plants had a major role in the origin and
115 evolution of *L. subulatum*. We also hypothesize that *L. subulatum* populations show substantial

116 genetic structure due to the spatial configuration of gypsum soils and the reproductive attributes
117 of the species.

118

119 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

120 *Habitat and species description—*

121 Gypsum plant communities in the Iberian Peninsula are mostly composed by chamaephytes and
122 ephemeral annual plants, with a large proportion of endemic species. In these systems, plants
123 form discrete patches immersed in a matrix of bare ground and biological soil crusts (BSC)
124 formed by cyanobacteria, lichens and mosses (Escudero et al., 2015).

125 The genus *Lepidium* L. is one of the largest in the Brassicaceae, with approximately 175
126 widespread plant species. Most of them are edaphic generalists, but two species, *Lepidium*
127 *subulatum* and *Lepidium cardamines*, are restricted to the gypsum soils of the Iberian Peninsula.
128 *Lepidium subulatum* L. (Brassicaceae) is one of the most common and widely distributed
129 gypsophiles in Iberian gypsum habitats (Romão and Escudero, 2005). It is a non-clonal
130 perennial shrub (20–60-cm high) endemic to the Iberian Peninsula and North Africa. This
131 species is mainly outcrossing with partial self-compatibility, as supported by both field
132 experiments (Gómez et al., 1996) and low inbreeding coefficients inferred from molecular
133 markers (Gómez-Fernández et al., 2016; Matesanz et al., 2018). It has entomophilous
134 pollination, being pollinated by a very rich community of generalist species from seven
135 different orders of insects (Santamaría et al., 2018). Seeds are released from very numerous
136 small fruits (silicles), lack obvious long-distance dispersal mechanisms and have a mucilage
137 that enhances seed adhesion to the soil (Romão and Escudero, 2005).

138

139 *Population sampling—*

140 We sampled 27 populations in the Iberian Peninsula and North Africa, spanning the worldwide
141 geographic and climatic distribution of *L. subulatum* (Table 1 and Fig. 1). Each population was
142 assigned to one of five different geographic zones that roughly match different river basins in
143 the Iberian Peninsula (Fig. 1) and are related to the main gypsum vegetation habitats described
144 in the region (Mota et al., 2011). Elevations of sampled populations varied from 219 (ALF) to
145 1157 m asl (TOP). The closest sampled populations (SMV and CHI) were 15 km apart and the
146 furthest populations (ARGL and BAL) were separated by 972 km. At each population, fresh
147 leaves of 20 individuals were collected and stored in paper bags, except for the Moroccan
148 population (MAR, 10 individuals), and the Peralta population (PER, 14 individuals). Leaves
149 were air-dried and stored until DNA extraction. Voucher specimens (one per sampled
150 population) were deposited at the herbarium of the Universidad Rey Juan Carlos (Móstoles,
151 Spain; Appendix S1, see Supplemental Data with this article). Additionally, 14 samples from
152 the same locality in Algeria (Chott Ech Chergui region) dating from 1884 to 1952 were obtained
153 from herbarium specimens (Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France; Appendix
154 S1). A total of 508 samples were included in the study. At each site, sampled individuals were
155 collected in a $\approx 20 \times 20$ m area at S – SE aspect to homogenize microenvironmental conditions
156 experienced by individuals. The south-oriented slopes of gypsum hills in the study region
157 receive more insolation and have lower water availability compared to north-oriented slopes.
158 Furthermore, gypsophiles are dominant and more abundant on slopes with S-SE aspects. All
159 populations had moderate to large size, from several hundred to several thousand individuals.
160 Individuals within populations were separated at least one meter from each other, to avoid
161 sampling closely-related individuals.

162 Climatic information of each population was extracted from CHELSA Bioclim layers
163 (Karger et al., 2017) using ArcMap 10.2.2 (ArcGIS Desktop, ESRI, Redlands, California,
164 USA). A 2 km buffer around each population was created to account for the within-site climatic

165 heterogeneity. Sampled populations spanned a wide climatic range: mean annual temperature
166 ranged from 11.4 to 16.9 °C and mean annual precipitation ranged from 254.7 to 647.8 mm
167 (Table 1).

168

169 ***DNA extraction, microsatellite markers, cpDNA markers and PCR conditions—***

170 Genomic DNA was extracted from 30 mg of air-dried leaf tissue, using a commercial kit
171 (DNeasy Plant Minikit; QIAGEN, California, USA) with minor changes to the manufacturer's
172 extraction protocol to improve the process. DNA extraction success was checked using 1%
173 agarose gels stained with GreenSafe Premium (NZYTech, Lisbon, Portugal). Ten species-
174 specific, nuclear polymorphic microsatellite markers previously described in Martínez-Nieto,
175 Merlo, Mota, Salmerón-Sánchez, & Segarra-Moragues (2012) were used to assess neutral
176 genetic diversity. Detailed information concerning microsatellite markers used and PCR
177 reactions is found in Appendix S2 and Appendix S3, respectively. Amplified DNA was
178 analyzed using an ABI 3730 (Applied Biosystems, Madrid, Spain) at “Unidad de Genómica y
179 Proteómica” of Universidad Complutense (Madrid, Spain), employing the GS500 size standard.

180 For phylogeographic analyses, we performed a preliminary screening with ten nuclear,
181 chloroplast, and mitochondrial loci widely used in phylogeographic studies (Appendix S4).
182 From this screening we selected the chloroplast *matK* gene and the *psbA-trnH* intergenic spacer
183 region because they showed relatively high variability at the population level. We sequenced
184 *matK* and *psbA-trnH* (henceforth referred to simply as *psbA*) from 8-10 individuals of each
185 study population. Additionally, we also sequenced the same regions in four individuals from
186 two different populations (Orusco de Tajuña and Portalrubio de Guadamejud, in the center of
187 the Iberian Peninsula) of *Lepidium cardamines* L., an Iberian gypsophile species that is a close
188 relative of *L. subulatum* (Mummenhoff et al., 2009), to evaluate whether the two species share
189 haplotypes indicative of processes like hybridization, chloroplast capture, and/or incomplete

190 lineage sorting that might confound interpretation of phylogeographic data (Schaal et al., 1998).
191 Finally, to test the monophyly and to date the origin of *L. subulatum*, we sequenced the nuclear
192 internal transcribed spacer (ITS) region and the chloroplast *trnT-trnL*, *trnL* intron and *trnL-trnF*
193 regions (Appendix S4), respectively, of one individual from four different *L. subulatum*
194 populations (BAL, ECZ, TDL, SMV) and one individual from one population (Orusco de
195 Tajuña) of *L. cardamines*. Detailed information concerning PCR conditions is found in
196 Appendix S3. Amplified DNA was sequenced at Macrogen DNA Sequencing Service (Madrid,
197 Spain).

198

199 ***Microsatellite genotyping and alignment of chloroplast sequences—***

200 Microsatellite scoring was performed using GeneMarker v2.2.0 (SoftGenetics, State College,
201 Pennsylvania, USA). Each sample was manually checked by three different researchers to
202 guarantee a robust scoring process. Different sizes of the amplified DNA fragments were
203 considered as different alleles. Every microsatellite locus exhibited polymorphic patterns,
204 yielding one (homozygous) or two alleles (heterozygous) per individual at each locus,
205 consistent with the ploidy level of the species. We repeated five percent of the samples to ensure
206 the repeatability of the scoring process. For population ARGL, only four individuals were
207 successfully genotyped. Therefore, this population was excluded from analyses of
208 microsatellite genetic diversity and population structure. We only considered in our analyses
209 the individuals for which at least 9 of 10 loci were successfully genotyped, representing 98.6%
210 of all individuals.

211 DNA sequences were manually trimmed, edited and cleaned using SEQUENCHER
212 5.4.6 (Gene Codes Corporation, Ann Arbor, Michigan, USA). A total of 207 individuals were
213 successfully sequenced for *matK* and 219 for *psbA*. We were able to concatenate *matK* and

214 *psbA* regions from 204 individuals, which were used in all downstream analyses. Sequence
215 alignment was performed in AliView (Larsson, 2014), with manual adjustments.

216

217 *Statistical analyses*—

218 *Phylogenetic analyses*—

219 To assess the evolutionary relationships between *L. subulatum* and other species of *Lepidium*
220 and to test the monophyly of *L. subulatum* (see other phylogenies in Beilstein, Nagalingum,
221 Clements, Manchester, & Mathews, 2010; Mummenhoff et al., 2009), we estimated
222 phylogenies of *Lepidium* using newly generated sequences of *L. subulatum* and *L. cardamines*
223 as well as publicly available sequences of other species of *Lepidium*, for the nuclear ITS region
224 and the chloroplast *matK* gene and *psbA* spacer region. For ITS, we included one individual
225 each from 4 populations of *L. subulatum* (BAL, ECZ, TDL, SMV) that covered the entire
226 geographic range of the species. We also included one individual from one population (Orusco
227 de Tajuña) of *L. cardamines*. We added these to all *Lepidium* ITS sequences available on
228 GenBank (Clark et al., 2016), which yielded 90 species from the genus in total (including *L.*
229 *subulatum* and *L. cardamines*). As outgroups, we downloaded GenBank ITS sequences for
230 seven *Arabidopsis* species and three *Cardaria* species. The total data set included 408
231 accessions, with 1-59 individuals per species (Appendix 1). Sequences were aligned as
232 described above, excluding the ambiguous regions for downstream analyses. Maximum
233 Likelihood (ML) analyses were conducted in RAxML (Stamatakis, 2014) using the CIPRES
234 Science Gateway v. 3.3 (Miller et al., 2010), selecting 1000 replicates, the GTRCAT model,
235 and rapid bootstrapping. We undertook similar ML analyses on the *matK* and *psbA* data
236 generated for phylogeographic analyses (described above). However, sequences of other taxa
237 of *Lepidium* beyond *L. subulatum* and *L. cardamines* were not available for inclusion.

238 To understand the temporal divergence of *L. subulatum*, we performed a molecular
239 dating analysis using the *trnT-trnL*, *trnL* intron and *trnL-trnF* regions for 68 different species
240 of *Lepidium* and 12 outgroup species (*Brassica napus*, *Cochlearia pyrenaica*, and ten species
241 of *Arabidopsis*; see Appendix 1). Sequence alignment was performed in Aliview, excluding the
242 ambiguous regions for further analysis. The dating analysis was performed in BEAST v1.10.4
243 (Suchard et al., 2018) using the CIPRES Science Gateway v. 3.3 (Miller et al., 2010). We
244 selected three different unlinked partitions with the HKY substitution model (Hasegawa et al.,
245 1985) for each partition. We used an uncorrelated lognormal relaxed clock model, which allows
246 uncorrelated rates of molecular evolution across the tree, and a birth-death process as tree prior
247 (Gernhard, 2008). We calibrated the tree at the basal node (the split point *Lepidium-*
248 *Arabidopsis*), using the date obtained by Guo et al., (2017) for the crown clade “A”: 16.9-20.3-
249 24 Mya, constraining the calibration point with a normal distribution with mean = 20.3 and
250 standard deviation = 2.0. Then, we ran a relaxed log-normal clock with default priors to estimate
251 prior distributions to be used in a second analysis that was used to estimate priors for the final
252 analysis. BEAST analyses were run for 40 million generations, logging parameters and trees
253 every 1000 generations. Convergence, mixing, and effective sample sizes (ESS) of parameters
254 were checked using Tracer v1.5.0 (Rambaut and Drummond, 2009). A burn-in of 1000 trees
255 was removed from each analysis. The remaining trees were used to generate a maximum clade
256 credibility tree with TreeAnnotator v1.8.2 (Rambaut and Drummond, 2014).

257

258 *Phylogeographic analyses—*

259 To evaluate phylogeographic patterns within *L. subulatum*, a haplotype network using the
260 concatenated *psbA* and *matK* sequences of each individual was estimated using PopART (Leigh
261 and Bryant, 2015) and employing the TCS method, which is appropriate to estimate genealogies
262 among populations (Clement et al., 2002). We also performed a ML phylogeny estimated from

263 RAxML (Stamatakis, 2014), using 10000 replicates, the GTRCAT model, and rapid
264 bootstrapping (Appendix S5).

265 To test the existence of historical demographic changes, Tajima's D (Tajima, 1989), Fu
266 and Li's F^* (Fu and Li, 1993) and Fu's F_S (Fu, 1997) statistics were calculated for each
267 population using DnaSP6 (Rozas et al., 2017). These tests were originally designed to assess
268 the neutrality of markers, but their combination is also useful to test departures from population
269 equilibrium due to historical demographic changes, bottlenecks or genetic hitchhiking (Fu,
270 1997). Thus, these tests allow for distinguishing the relative role of demographic changes or
271 other processes (like gene flow or mutation) in shaping the allele frequencies of populations.
272 While significant and positive Tajima's D values can inform us about the admixture of two
273 different populations, significant and negative Tajima's D values indicate a recent bottleneck
274 in a population (Tajima, 1989; Aris-Brosou and Excoffier, 1996). Fu's F_S is also used to test
275 for demographic expansion and it is described as more sensitive to the growth of the populations
276 than Tajima's D (Chávez-Pesqueira and Núñez-Farfán, 2016). These tests may be performed
277 only if the populations possess more than one haplotype.

278

279 *Intrapopulation genetic diversity—*

280 We checked the presence of null alleles and genotyping errors such as allele dropouts or false
281 positive alleles due to stuttering in the nuclear microsatellites dataset, using Micro-Checker
282 2.2.3 (Van Oosterhout et al., 2004). No genotyping errors or null alleles were detected. For each
283 population, we calculated the following genetic diversity indices: P , proportion of polymorphic
284 loci; A , allele richness (mean number of alleles per locus); A_{rare} , mean number of rarefied alleles
285 per locus; A_e , mean number of effective alleles; H_o , observed heterozygosity ($H_o = 1 -$
286 $\sum_k \sum_i P_{kii}/np$, Nei, 1987); H_e , expected heterozygosity ($H_e = \tilde{n}/(\tilde{n} - 1)[1 - \sum_i \bar{p}_i^2 -$
287 $H_o/2\tilde{n}]$, Nei, 1987); F_{IS} , inbreeding coefficient; β , neutral genetic differentiation between

288 populations (from 0 to 1; Weir & Hill, 2002); the number of private alleles and the number of
289 multilocus genotypes. A , A_{rare} , H_o , H_e , F_{IS} (and their confidence intervals) and β were calculated
290 using the functions *nb.alleles*, *allelic.richness*, *basic.stats*, *boot.ppfis* and *betas*, respectively,
291 from the package hierfstat (Goudet and Jombart, 2015) as implemented in R (R Core Team,
292 2018). Rarefaction allowed for calculating the mean number of alleles per locus (A_{rare})
293 considering equal sample sizes in all populations (note that MAR only had 10 individuals
294 sampled). A_e was calculated using the function *genetic_diversity* (package gstudio; Dyer, 2016),
295 the number of private alleles was calculated using the function *private_alleles* and the number
296 of multilocus genotypes was calculated using function *poppr*, both in package poppr (Kamvar
297 et al., 2014).

298 Genetic diversity of chloroplast markers was assessed using DnaSP6 (Rozas et al.,
299 2017). For each population, we calculated the number of segregating sites, the number of
300 haplotypes, haplotype diversity (Hd) and nucleotide diversity (π).

301

302 *Population structure—*

303 To assess population differentiation we calculated a pairwise F_{ST} matrix based on microsatellite
304 markers using the *genet.dist* function (package hierfstat, Goudet & Jombart, 2015). The matrix
305 of pairwise Nei's (D) differences between populations from chloroplast markers was calculated
306 using the *pairnei* function (package haplotypes; Aktas, 2015). We also calculated a Euclidean
307 geographical distance matrix between populations, performed with ecodist package (Goslee
308 and Urban, 2007), using the UTM coordinates of each population.

309 To assess the distribution of genetic variation of microsatellite and chloroplast markers
310 across regions and populations, we used Analysis of Molecular Variance (AMOVA, Excoffier,
311 Smouse, & Quattro, 1992). AMOVAs were performed using the *poppr.amova* function
312 (package poppr, Kamvar et al., 2014), with 99999 permutations and excluding within-

313 individual variation. We performed two different AMOVAs: 1) Non-hierarchical AMOVA,
314 considering all populations within the same region; 2) Hierarchical AMOVA, assigning each
315 population to each of five geographical zones (Fig. 1).

316 To assess whether closer populations are more genetically similar, we tested for
317 isolation by distance (IBD). We performed two different Mantel correlograms (Legendre and
318 Legendre, 2012), using the pairwise genetic distance matrix calculated from microsatellite
319 markers and from chloroplast markers and the pairwise geographical distance matrix between
320 populations. While Mantel tests show the overall relationship between the genetic and the
321 geographic matrix, a Mantel correlogram compares the pairwise genetic distance matrix (F_{ST} in
322 our case) and the pairwise geographical distance matrix (Euclidean distance), which allow for
323 finding significant correlations between them at different distance classes. Each distance class
324 includes all pairs of points that are included within a specific distance. A correlation index
325 (Mantel statistic, r_M) between genetic and geographical distance matrices is calculated for each
326 distance class. The size and number of distance classes was set using Sturge's rule (Legendre
327 and Legendre, 2012). Significance was tested using 99999 permutations. Mantel correlograms
328 were generated using the *mantel.correlog* function (package *vegan*, Oksanen et al., 2019).

329 Population genetic structure from microsatellite markers was further evaluated using the
330 Bayesian clustering algorithm in STRUCTURE v. 2.3. (Pritchard et al., 2000). This method
331 evaluates the membership of each individual to a specific genetic cluster (K). We performed 10
332 independent runs for each K (from $K = 1$ to $K = 30$), with a burn-in period of 10^5 iterations and
333 10^6 MCMC iterations after the burn-in period, using the admixture model, where individuals
334 from different K values could have a common ancestry (Falush et al., 2003), as recommended
335 for microsatellites. We ran STRUCTURE assuming correlated and independent allele
336 frequencies (Pritchard et al., 2000; Falush et al., 2003) and both methods provided very similar
337 clustering results. STRUCTURE results were extracted using Structure Harvester (Earl and

338 vonHoldt, 2012), which were then used to generate CLUMPP input files. Then, using CLUMPP
339 1.1.2 (Jakobsson and Rosenberg, 2007), results from 10 runs of each K were combined, using
340 the Greedy algorithm. Membership of each individual to a specific genetic cluster was
341 visualized using DISTRICT 1.1 (Rosenberg, 2004). To ensure the assignment performed by
342 STRUCTURE, we repeated the clustering assignment with rMavericK (Verity and Nichols,
343 2016), obtaining virtually the same assignment results.

344 Some recent work has drawn attention to the problems related to determining the
345 appropriate number of genetic clusters (K) (Meirmans, 2015; Janes et al., 2017). To determine
346 this, we first considered the average log probability (L_K) of the data for each K , and determined
347 the value of K for which this probability is maximized (Pritchard et al., 2000). We also
348 calculated the optimum value of K using the Evanno method (Evanno et al., 2005) implemented
349 in Structure Harvester (Earl and vonHoldt, 2012). This *ad hoc* method is based on changes in
350 the mean values of log probability of data at successive K values. The Evanno method and L_K
351 simplify model assumptions because these methods obtain the value of K for each assignment
352 model, so estimating the optimum value of K requires comparison between models, which is
353 not straightforward (Verity and Nichols, 2016). Thus, we also calculated K using rMavericK.
354 This software uses generalized thermodynamic integration (GTI), which has been hypothesized
355 to be more accurate and precise (Verity and Nichols, 2016). Therefore, K was calculated using
356 rMavericK, although L_K and Evanno methods provided similar results (Appendix S6).

357

358 **RESULTS**

359 *Analyses of sequence data—*

360 Information on lengths and sequence variation for all sequence alignments is provided in
361 Appendix S7. In both the ITS (Appendix S8) and chloroplast (*trnT-trnL*, *trnL* intron and *trnL*-
362 *trnF*; Fig. 2) trees, *Lepidium subulatum* was sister to the Iberian gypsophile *L. cardamines* (ITS

363 bootstrap support = 97%; chloroplast Bayesian posterior probability = 95%). In the ITS tree,
364 all sequences of *L. subulatum* formed a clade with high support (bootstrap support = 98%). In
365 the *matK/psbA* tree (Appendix S5), haplotypes of *L. subulatum* and *L. cardamines* were
366 relatively distant from each other and none were shared between the two species. The molecular
367 dating analysis based on the chloroplast loci dated the evolutionary divergence of *L. subulatum*
368 from 5.08 – 1.33 Mya (mean = 3.01 Mya; Fig. 2). Furthermore, the divergence of the gypsophile
369 clade of *L. subulatum* and *L. cardamines* was dated to 5.96 – 2.05 Mya (mean = 3.86 Mya).

370 Haplotype analyses recovered 22 different haplotypes and 19 segregating sites (*S*). Total
371 nucleotide (π) and total haplotype diversity (*Hd*) across populations was 0.0038 and 0.747,
372 respectively. Twelve populations possessed more than one haplotype, while 15 populations
373 possessed one fixed haplotype for all sampled individuals (Table 2).

374 The haplotype network showed that *L. subulatum* was connected to its closest relative
375 *L. cardamines* by three mutation steps, with no shared haplotypes between the two species (Fig.
376 3). The network was complex, with one loop and three extinct or unsampled haplotypes. Despite
377 the complexity of the network, we identified four common haplotypes. The most frequent
378 haplotype (haplotype A, in blue), was found in 16 populations (in nine of them it was the only
379 haplotype present) and was distributed broadly across the Iberian Peninsula (in the north-west,
380 the center and the south). The second most common haplotype (haplotype B, in red) was
381 separated from haplotype A by one mutational step and was found mainly in 4 populations of
382 the eastern Iberian Peninsula: CAB, PDG, VAL and YEB, and one individual from VY
383 population. The third most common haplotype was haplotype C (in purple), which was
384 restricted to the Ebro River Valley. This haplotype was the most divergent, being separated by
385 many mutational steps from all other main haplotypes. The fourth most common haplotype was
386 haplotype D (in yellow), which was restricted to North Africa (ARGL and MAR) and was the

387 only haplotype found in this region. Overall, the center of the Iberian Peninsula showed the
388 highest haplotype diversity.

389 We obtained very similar results from the phylogenetic tree based on *psbA* and *matK*.
390 Although some of the groups were identical between the tree and the network, the low support
391 values of some branches in the tree showed the uncertainty of relationships among some
392 haplotypes (*e.g.*, see green haplotypes in Fig. 3 and Appendix S5).

393 The Mantel Correlogram based on the chloroplast markers showed that the closest
394 populations (first distance class, 62.15 km) were significantly similar (Fig. 4a; $R_M = 0.181$, p -
395 value = 0.010), and populations separated by ~350 km were statistically different (Fig. 4a; R_M
396 = -0.176, p -value = 0.041), confirming the presence of isolation by distance.

397 The non-hierarchical AMOVA of chloroplast loci performed with all individuals and
398 populations showed a variation of 46.08% among populations and 53.92% within them (p -value
399 < 0.001; Table 3). In the hierarchical AMOVA with populations grouped by their geographic
400 location, 32.82% of the variation was explained by the geographic region (p -value < 0.001;
401 Table 3).

402 In the populations with more than one haplotype, overall Tajima's D , F_u and Li's F^* and
403 F_s were not statistically different from 0 (p -value > 0.05), except for SMV, which showed
404 a significantly positive Tajima's D value (*i.e.*, a higher average pairwise differences observed
405 than expected; Table 2). Therefore, our results suggest the admixture of two distant populations
406 in SMV population; and we did not detect demographic changes in the other populations.

407

408 ***Microsatellite analyses—***

409 We found 145 different alleles among the 504 individuals, for an average of 14.5 alleles per
410 locus. The number of alleles per locus ranged from six (Locus 10 and 11) to 24 (Locus 4).
411 Microsatellite genetic diversity was high for all populations (Table 4). Most populations

412 possessed 100% polymorphic loci, except for AGR, SMV, SPP and YEB, with 90%
413 polymorphic loci. Expected heterozygosity ranged from 0.452 (SEG) to 0.681 (BAZ; Table 4).
414 Observed heterozygosity varied from 0.415 (SPP) to 0.718 (PER; Table 4). The fixation index
415 F_{IS} was low for all populations, ranging from -0.193 (PER, showing a heterozygote excess) to
416 0.237 (BAZ) and none of the populations had a F_{IS} statistically different from 0. Population-
417 specific F_{ST} (β) varied from 0.064 (BAZ) to 0.379 (SEG; Table 4). The average number of
418 alleles per locus (A) ranged from 3.3 (SEG) to 7.1 (BAZ), with an overall average of 5.15 alleles
419 per locus. The rarefied mean number of alleles per locus (A_{rare}) ranged from 2.62 (CAB
420 population) to 5.65 (BAZ population), with an overall average of 4.40 alleles per locus. The
421 mean number of effective alleles per locus (A_e) varied from 1.93 (SEG) to 3.89 (BEL), with an
422 overall average of 3.06 effective alleles per locus. The number of multilocus genotypes matched
423 the number of individuals sampled in each population, except for ARA and SPP, where there
424 were two individuals with the same genotype. We found a total of 23 private alleles in 15 of the
425 26 populations, ranging from one to three per population.

426

427 *Microsatellite population structure—*

428 Pairwise F_{ST} values were generally low, ranging from very low (0.030) between populations
429 CHI and SMV to high (0.440) between populations SEG and SPP (Appendix S9). Results from
430 rMavericK clearly supported the presence of three different genetic clusters ($K=3$). L_K and the
431 Evanno method supported $K=2$ but also $K=3$ (Appendix S6). Thus, we selected $K=3$ that
432 allowed a clearer interpretation of the data. Based on the $K=3$ solution, most of the populations
433 included admixed individuals assigned to more than one genetic cluster. Four populations from
434 the Tajo river basin (ARA, BEL, SPP and YEB) and one from the Guadalquivir-Júcar-Segura
435 basins (CAB) contained individuals that were mostly assigned to one genetic cluster (blue, Fig.
436 5). Individuals from AGR, BAL, ECZ, PDG, TDL, TOR and VAL were mostly assigned to a

437 different genetic cluster (yellow, Fig. 5). Individuals from APG, BAZ, PER, TOP and VY were
438 mostly assigned to the magenta genetic cluster (Fig. 5). Finally, individuals from ALF, AZQ,
439 CHI, GEL, MAR, PEÑ, SEG, SMV and TER belonged to two or even three different genetic
440 clusters (frequently a mixture of the magenta and yellow genetic clusters; Fig. 5).

441 The non-hierarchical AMOVA with all individuals and populations showed that 81.37%
442 of variation was found within populations and 18.63% between populations (p-value < 0.001;
443 Table 3). There was a small but significant population structure explained by the geographical
444 location of the populations. In the geographic AMOVA, 2.95% of the variation was explained
445 by the geographic region (p-value < 0.001; Table 3).

446 The Mantel correlogram based on microsatellites did not show evidence of isolation by
447 distance (IBD). Only the closest populations (first distance class, 58.55 km) were significantly
448 similar (Fig. 4b; $R_M = 0.151$, p-value = 0.023).

449

450 **DISCUSSION**

451 Our molecular dating results suggest that the Iberian gypsophilic clade composed by *Lepidium*
452 *subulatum* and *L. cardamines* originated ~ 3.86 Mya (5.96-2.05 Mya) and the stem lineage of
453 *L. subulatum* diverged ~3.01 Mya (5.08-1.33 Mya). Thus, it is likely that the specialization to
454 gypsum soils (gypsophily) in this group appeared at some point from the latest Miocene to the
455 early Pleistocene, in the ancestor of both species. Furthermore, these dates for the divergence
456 of the study species in the Plio-Pleistocene also suggest that the paleoclimatic and geological
457 events that occurred in the Mediterranean Basin around this period could be associated with the
458 origin and further expansion of this gypsophile. First, the massive emergence at the surface of
459 gypsum soils during the Neogene consequence of evaporitic processes in the region (Escavy et
460 al., 2012) increased the probability of colonizing a novel edaphic habitat by chance (chance
461 dispersal *sensu* Rajakaruna, 2017; Escudero et al., 2015; Moore & Jansen, 2007), likely

462 facilitating the evolution of gypsum-restricted taxa. Second, the progressive aridification of the
463 Mediterranean basin before and during the Messinian salinity crisis (~6-5 Mya) not only
464 favored the creation of gypsum soils, but also probably acted as an evolutionary force
465 promoting the evolution of *L. subulatum* and other gypsophiles in the new climatic conditions
466 (Thompson, 2005). It has been hypothesized that certain gypsophiles may have been preadapted
467 to the global aridification that started in the mid-Miocene that subsequently colonized gypsum
468 soils (Escudero et al., 2015 and references therein). However, the availability of gypsum soils
469 in the Iberian Peninsula prior to our estimated date of origin (Escavy et al., 2012) suggests that
470 this is not the case for *L. subulatum*. The relatively old date of origin of the species would
471 provide enough time to colonize isolated gypsum patches and is congruent with its widespread
472 distribution in the Iberian Peninsula, even moreso when its inefficient dispersal ability is
473 considered (Escudero, Iriondo, Olano, Rubio, & Somolinos, 2000; see Moore & Jansen 2007
474 for similar patterns). Our results also agree with the estimated age of other Iberian and non-
475 Iberian gypsophiles. The clade that includes *Helianthemum squamatum* (L.) Dum. Cours.
476 started its diversification 4.37 Mya (8.57 – 1.65 Mya; Aparicio et al., 2017) and the clade
477 formed by *Ferula loscosii* (Lange) Willk. and its sister species diverged from their common
478 ancestor 4 Mya (6.4 – 1.6 Mya; Pérez-Collazos et al., 2009). Other North American gypsophiles
479 such as *Tiquilia hispidissima* (Torr. & A. Gray) A.T. Richardson split from its nearest relatives
480 in the early/mid-Pliocene (5 – 3.5 Mya; Moore and Jansen, 2007).

481 The evolutionary distinctiveness of *Lepidium subulatum* and *L. cardamines* in both the
482 haplotype network and the ITS phylogeny is important because it reinforces the idea that past
483 edaphic and climatic changes could be important in the origin of *L. subulatum*, compared to
484 other evolutionary processes. The two species did not share haplotypes, which is consistent
485 with a lack of hybridization between both species that could have resulted in chloroplast capture
486 (Schaal et al., 1998). Nevertheless, it is important to note that existing population sampling of

487 *L. cardamines* is limited and additional sampling may reveal shared haplotypes between the
488 two species. Some authors have noted the importance of hybridization in the origin of edaphic
489 specialists (Rajakaruna, 2017 and references therein), but Ellstrand, Whitkus, & Rieseberg,
490 (1996) reported that Brassicaceae taxa are not particularly prone to natural hybridization.
491 Several aspects, including differences in their reproductive phenology (Hernández Bermejo and
492 Clemente, 1993) may have served to minimize potential hybridization between them.

493 Based on the haplotype analysis, *L. subulatum* may have originated in the center of the
494 Iberian Peninsula. This region shows the highest haplotype diversity (see also individual *psbA*
495 and *matK* haplotype networks in Appendix S10), suggesting that populations in this region have
496 had enough time to reach such high diversity. Furthermore, gypsum outcrops of the Tajo Valley
497 present the greatest climatic variation of the entire distribution range, which could also explain
498 the high genetic diversity found in this region. The populations of the Ebro Valley (purple
499 shades in Fig. 3) possessed the most distantly related haplotypes, which indicates that gene flow
500 via seeds between the Ebro Valley and the rest of the Iberian Peninsula has likely been limited
501 during the evolutionary history of *L. subulatum* (see Fig. 1 and Appendix S10).

502 Interestingly, North Africa populations (MAR and ARGL) are fixed for a single
503 haplotype that is closely related to the most common one. It is thus likely that the colonization
504 of North Africa occurred via a recent, long-distance dispersal event from the Iberian Peninsula.
505 Several pieces of evidence support this claim. First, our analysis estimated the mean date of
506 origin of the species after the Messinian Salinity Crisis, when the Iberian Peninsula and North
507 Africa were disconnected again by the Mediterranean Sea. Second, if *L. subulatum* had been
508 isolated in North Africa for at least 6-5 My (during the Messinian Salinity Crisis, when the
509 Mediterranean Sea was desiccated) we would expect a greater haplotype diversity in North
510 Africa or, alternatively, only one, much more divergent haplotype. Our results match those of
511 other studies that have found that populations from both sides of the Mediterranean Sea were

512 closely related as a consequence of long-distance dispersal events between the Iberian Peninsula
513 and North Africa (Terrab et al., 2008), suggesting that these events have not been rare within
514 the Mediterranean region (see Nieto Feliner, 2014 and references therein).

515 In our analyses, we did not detect significant demographic changes at the species level,
516 although 15 populations showed a fixed haplotype. These fixed populations likely experienced
517 bottlenecks caused by founder effects, likely reflecting the poor seed dispersal ability of the
518 species. However, *L. subulatum* showed high chloroplast genetic diversity at the species level.
519 This high haplotype diversity observed across populations in the chloroplast markers was also
520 coupled with high overall genetic diversity in microsatellite markers. Furthermore, *L.*
521 *subulatum* also exhibited high microsatellite intrapopulation diversity in all populations. These
522 high values of genetic diversity are congruent with the current high number of individuals at
523 each population, which may reach up to several thousand plants (personal observation). The
524 effective population size of organelle genes is lower than that of nuclear genes (Petit et al.,
525 2005), which could explain the slightly higher values of genetic diversity found in
526 microsatellites markers in some populations. Some authors have reported that edaphic
527 specialists may be composed of genetically depauperate populations due to the specialization
528 to the substrate (see Rajakaruna, 2017 for a deeper discussion), and as such, they may constitute
529 evolutionary dead-ends. However, our results for this species show that this is not necessarily
530 the case, and agree with other studies that also found high levels of genetic diversity at the
531 landscape level in both Iberian (Matesanz et al., 2019) and non-Iberian gypsophiles (Aguirre-
532 Liguori et al., 2014).

533 Even though genetic variation was high regardless of the type of marker, we found
534 contrasting results for the population genetic structure inferred by microsatellites and
535 chloroplast markers. We observed significant genetic structure in both markers, but greater
536 geographic structure in chloroplast loci. We are aware that comparing markers with different

537 number of alleles and/or different mutation rates (e.g. nuclear microsatellites and chloroplast
538 sequence data) could bias the comparison of genetic differentiation among populations
539 (Meirmans, 2006; Jost, 2008; Verity & Nichols 2014). Jost (2008) proposed D_{est} as a nearly
540 unbiased estimator to assess genetic differentiation between populations accounting for
541 different allele numbers. The calculated D_{est} values of nuclear and chloroplast markers for our
542 populations are virtually identical to the computed F_{ST} values (see Appendix S11), suggesting
543 that the large difference in population structure is not an artifact due to the choice of markers,
544 but rather, it is due to eco-evolutionary processes. Because chloroplast DNA is maternally
545 inherited and nuclear DNA is biparentally inherited in our species, it is likely that the greater
546 genetic structure observed in the chloroplast data indicates that gene flow via pollen is higher
547 than via seeds in *L. subulatum*. Indeed, using the indices of population differentiation (F_{ST} and
548 G_{ST}) calculated for both markers types, and applying Ennos' equation (see Appendix S12), we
549 estimated an effective gene flow via pollen between ~2-10 times higher than via seeds, agreeing
550 with studies reporting that pollen flow is usually higher than seed flow (Petit et al., 2005).

551 However, we did not expect such large restrictions to the movement of seeds among
552 populations in this system. In a field study assessing the role of grazing in gypsum plant
553 communities, Pueyo et al., (2008) found that livestock act as effective seed dispersal agents
554 between fragments. Accordingly, livestock practices, which often involve the movement of
555 cattle across different geographical regions in the Iberian Peninsula (Azcárate et al., 2013),
556 could have favored the movement of seeds between different *L. subulatum* populations,
557 reducing the high genetic structure found in chloroplast markers. However, our results show
558 limited seed dispersal, particularly between geographical regions. Specifically, the populations
559 from the Ebro Valley and North Africa were strongly different from all other populations, as
560 shown by the isolation by distance among different regions, suggesting that animals are likely
561 not playing a key role in the movement of seeds in our system, at least when long distances are

562 considered. Despite the importance of transhumance in the Iberian Peninsula, drove roads of
563 the Ebro Valley never have been connected to all others main drove roads (see Fig. 1 in
564 Manzano & Casas, 2010), which could have increased the differences between this region and
565 the rest of the Iberian Peninsula. Furthermore, several nearby populations in the same
566 geographic region did not share haplotypes (see Tajo Valley in Fig. 3), which shows limited
567 seed dispersal even across short distances. These results may also be explained by the fact that,
568 similar to other gypsophiles, seeds of *L. subulatum* lack obvious long-distance dispersal
569 mechanisms (Escudero et al., 2000; Moore and Jansen, 2007). Therefore, our results also
570 suggest that seed movement between distant areas may only be possible by chance long-
571 distance dispersal events. The Iberian Mountain Range, which separates the Ebro Basin
572 populations from all others, could restrict seed movement between the populations from the
573 Ebro Basin and all the other populations, accounting for the high genetic differences observed
574 between this region and the rest. Similarly, the presence of the Mediterranean Sea may also
575 block seed dispersal from the Iberian Peninsula to North Africa, explaining the distinctive
576 haplotype in these populations.

577 Conversely, pollen movement does not appear to have been strongly limited between
578 populations or geographical regions, as shown by the assignment of individuals from
579 populations from different geographical regions to the same genetic cluster in microsatellite
580 analyses (Fig. 5). High pollen flow among populations and regions could be favored by the
581 presence of numerous patches of gypsum habitat among populations that would increase their
582 connectivity, allowing an efficient movement of different pollinators between populations
583 (Santamaría et al., 2018; Matesanz et al., 2019). *Lepidium subulatum* presents an advanced
584 phenology compared to other species of gypsum ecosystems (Hernández Bermejo and
585 Clemente, 1993; Matesanz et al., 2018) and it is possible that pollinators could actively seek
586 the flowering plants at this early season, facilitating pollen flow to further distances.

587 Interestingly, in a few instances populations within the same region (sometimes located less
588 than 50 km apart) possessed individuals that were assigned to different genetic clusters (Fig.
589 5). Although we cannot pinpoint the exact processes that modulate this complex pattern, several
590 factors, including uneven pollen flow between populations, differential barriers to pollen flow
591 at small scales, differences in connectivity among populations and population size could be
592 responsible for this pattern (Aguilar et al., 2008).

593

594 **CONCLUSIONS**

595 Our results show how paleoclimatic and geological changes in Plio-Pleistocene could be
596 important in the origin and evolution of *L. subulatum*. The contrasting pattern of genetic
597 structure found in the nuclear and chloroplast markers, suggesting lower seed flow among
598 populations compared to pollen flow, also highlight the importance of using both maternally
599 and biparentally inherited markers to fully understand the phylogeography of plant species.
600 Furthermore, the species exhibited high values of genetic diversity in both markers, especially
601 in microsatellites. Our results suggest that regionally dominant gypsophiles like *L. subulatum*
602 have had broad distributions and maintained high effective population sizes during their
603 evolutionary history, suggesting that these gypsophilic taxa are relatively old. Although the
604 markers used in this study inform us about the neutral genetic diversity of the populations, if
605 neutral genetic diversity and quantitative genetic diversity were correlated in populations of *L.*
606 *subulatum*, our results would suggest the existence of adaptive potential to cope with changing
607 conditions. In this context, further studies should focus on the levels of quantitative genetic
608 variation of populations and whether it is influenced by the geographical location or the
609 evolutionary history of the populations.

610

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625 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS**

626 M.B.-S., A.E., and S.M. conceived and designed the study; M.B.-S., M.R.-M., B.P., A.G.-F.
627 and S.M. collected leaf samples; M.B.-S., M.R.-M., L.P. and I.I. performed the laboratory work.
628 M.B.-S., M.J.M., A.G.-F., M.P. and S.M. performed the statistical analysis and contributed to
629 the interpretation of the results; M.B.-S. led the writing of the manuscript with input from all
630 other authors.

631

632 **DATA AVAILABILITY**

633 Raw DNA data, microsatellite scoring, final chloroplast DNA sequence assembly and climatic
634 data are available on Figshare (<https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.c.5132882>). New generated
635 DNA sequences of *L. subulatum* and *L. cardamines* from different markers used in this study
636 have been submitted to GenBank (*psbA L. subulatum*: MW044696 – MW044914; *psbA L.*

637 *cardamines*: MW048746 – MW048748; *matK L. subulatum*: MW119359 – MW119565; *matK*
638 *L. cardamines*: MW048759 – MW048761; ITS *L. subulatum*: MW067154 – MW067157; ITS
639 *L. cardamines*: MW058062; *trnL* intron *L. subulatum*: MW048753 – MW048755; *trnL* intron
640 *L. cardamines*: MW048749 – MW048750; *trnL-trnF L. subulatum*: MW048756 – MW048758;
641 *trnL-trnF L. cardamines*: MW048751 – MW048752).

642

643 **SUPPORTING INFORMATION**

644 Additional Supporting Information may be found online in the supporting information section
645 at the end of the article.

646 APPENDIX S1. Voucher accessions of used specimens.

647 APPENDIX S2. Detailed information of microsatellite loci used.

648 APPENDIX S3. Detailed information of PCR reactions.

649 APPENDIX S4. Molecular markers used in the preliminary screening and selected for our
650 study.

651 APPENDIX S5. Maximum Likelihood phylogenetic tree based on concatenated *matK* and *psbA*
652 sequences.

653 APPENDIX S6. Graphics of the tests used to select the appropriate number of genetic clusters.

654 APPENDIX S7. Final length of the alignments used in this study.

655 APPENDIX S8. Maximum Likelihood phylogenetic tree of *Lepidium* based on ITS sequences.

656 APPENDIX S9. Pairwise F_{ST} matrix from nuclear microsatellites for all sampled populations.

657 APPENDIX S10. Haplotype networks individually performed for *psbA* and *matK* loci.

658 APPENDIX S11. D_{est} values of nuclear and chloroplast markers and their comparison with F_{ST}
659 values.

660 APPENDIX S12. Population differentiation indices of chloroplast and nuclear markers and
661 ratio pollen flow-seeds flow.

663 **LITERATURE CITED**

- 664 Aguilar, R., M. Quesada, L. Ashworth, Y. Herrerias-Diego, and J. Lobo. 2008. Genetic
 665 consequences of habitat fragmentation in plant populations: Susceptible signals in plant
 666 traits and methodological approaches. *Molecular Ecology* 17: 5177–5188.
- 667 Aguirre-Liguori, J. A., E. Scheinvar, and L. E. Eguiarte. 2014. Gypsum soil restriction drives
 668 genetic differentiation in *Fouquieria shrevei* (Fouquieriaceae). *American Journal of*
 669 *Botany* 101: 730–736.
- 670 Aktas, C. 2015. Haplotypes: haplotype inference and statistical analysis of genetic variation.
 671 *R package version 1*.
- 672 Aparicio, A., S. Martín-Hernanz, C. Parejo-Farnés, J. Arroyo, S. Lavergne, E. B. Yeşilyurt,
 673 M. L. Zhang, et al. 2017. Phylogenetic reconstruction of the genus *Helianthemum*
 674 (Cistaceae) using plastid and nuclear dna-sequences: Systematic and evolutionary
 675 inferences. *Taxon* 66: 868–885.
- 676 Aris-Brosou, S., and L. Excoffier. 1996. The impact of population expansion and mutation
 677 rate heterogeneity on DNA sequence polymorphism. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*
 678 13: 494–504.
- 679 Avise, J. 2000. John C. Avise - Phylogeography_ The History and Formation of Species-
 680 Harvard University Press (2000).pdf. 455.
- 681 Azcárate, F. M., I. Robleño, J. Seoane, P. Manzano, and B. Peco. 2013. Drove roads as local
 682 biodiversity reservoirs: Effects on landscape pattern and plant communities in a
 683 Mediterranean region. *Applied Vegetation Science* 16: 480–490.
- 684 Beilstein, M. A., N. S. Nagalingum, M. D. Clements, S. R. Manchester, and S. Mathews.
 685 2010. Dated molecular phylogenies indicate a Miocene origin for *Arabidopsis thaliana*.
 686 *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 107:
 687 18724–18728.
- 688 Blondel, J., J. Aronson, J.-Y. Bodiou, and G. Boeuf. 2010. The Mediterranean Region -
 689 Biological Diversity in Space and Time. *Oxford University Press*: 401.
- 690 Chávez-Pesqueira, M., and J. Núñez-Farfán. 2016. Genetic diversity and structure of wild
 691 populations of *Carica papaya* in Northern Mesoamerica inferred by nuclear
 692 microsatellites and chloroplast markers. *Annals of Botany* 118: 1293–1306.
- 693 Clark, K., I. Karsch-Mizrachi, D. J. Lipman, J. Ostell, and E. W. Sayers. 2016. GenBank.
 694 *Nucleic Acids Research* 44: D67–D72.
- 695 Clement, M. J., Q. Snell, P. Walker, D. Posada, and K. A. Crandall. 2002. TCS: estimating
 696 gene genealogies. ipdps, 184.
- 697 van Dam, J. A. 2006. Geographic and temporal patterns in the late Neogene (12-3 Ma)
 698 aridification of Europe: The use of small mammals as paleoprecipitation proxies.
 699 *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 238: 190–218.
- 700 Dyer, R. J. 2016. gstudio: Tools related to the spatial analysis of genetic marker data. *R*
 701 *package version 1*.
- 702 Earl, D. A., and B. M. vonHoldt. 2012. STRUCTURE HARVESTER: A website and program
 703 for visualizing STRUCTURE output and implementing the Evanno method.
 704 *Conservation Genetics Resources* 4: 359–361.
- 705 Ellstrand, N. C., R. Whitkus, and L. H. Rieseberg. 1996. Distribution of spontaneous plant
 706 hybrids. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 93: 5090–5093.
- 707 Ennos, R. A., A. Langdon, X.-S. Hu, and W. F. Sinclair. 1999. Using organelle markers to
 708 elucidate the history, ecology and evolution of plant populations. *Molecular systematics*
 709 *and plant evolution*: 1–19.

- 710 Escavy, J. I., M. J. Herrero, and M. E. Arribas. 2012. Gypsum resources of Spain: Temporal
711 and spatial distribution. *Ore Geology Reviews* 49: 72–84.
- 712 Escudero, A., J. M. Iriondo, J. M. Olano, A. Rubio, and R. C. Somolinos. 2000. Factors
713 affecting establishment of a gypsophyte: The case of *Lepidium subulatum*
714 (Brassicaceae). *American Journal of Botany* 87: 861–871.
- 715 Escudero, A., S. Palacio, F. T. Maestre, and A. L. Luzuriaga. 2015. Plant life on gypsum: a
716 review of its multiple facets. *Biological Reviews* 90: 1–18.
- 717 Evanno, G., S. Regnaut, and J. Goudet. 2005. Detecting the number of clusters of individuals
718 using the software STRUCTURE: a simulation study. *Molecular ecology* 14: 2611–
719 2620.
- 720 Excoffier, L., P. E. Smouse, and J. M. Quattro. 1992. Analysis of molecular variance inferred
721 from metric distances among DNA haplotypes: application to human mitochondrial
722 DNA restriction data. *Genetics* 131: 479–491.
- 723 Falush, D., M. Stephens, and J. K. Pritchard. 2003. Inference of Population Structure Using
724 Multilocus Genotype Data : Linked Loci and Correlated Allele Frequencies. 1587: 1567–
725 1587.
- 726 Fu, Y.-X. 1997. Statistical tests of neutrality of mutations against population growth,
727 hitchhiking and background selection. *Genetics* 147: 915–925.
- 728 Fu, Y.-X., and W.-H. Li. 1993. Statistical tests of neutrality of mutations. *Genetics* 133: 693–
729 709.
- 730 Garcia-Castellanos, D., and A. Villaseñor. 2011. Messinian salinity crisis regulated by
731 competing tectonics and erosion at the Gibraltar arc. *Nature* 480: 359–363.
- 732 Gernhard, T. 2008. The conditioned reconstructed process. *Journal of Theoretical Biology*
733 253: 769–778.
- 734 Gómez-Fernández, A., I. Alcocer, and S. Matesanz. 2016. Does higher connectivity lead to
735 higher genetic diversity? Effects of habitat fragmentation on genetic variation and
736 population structure in a gypsophile. *Conservation Genetics* 17: 631–641.
- 737 Gómez, J. M., R. Zamora, J. A. Hódar, and D. García. 1996. Experimental study of
738 pollination by ants in Mediterranean high mountain and arid habitats. *Oecologia* 105:
739 236–242.
- 740 Goslee, S. C., and D. L. Urban. 2007. The ecodist package for dissimilarity-based analysis of
741 ecological data. *Journal of Statistical Software* 22: 1–19.
- 742 Goudet, J., and T. Jombart. 2015. Estimation and tests of hierarchical F-statistics. R Core
743 Team.
- 744 Guo, X., J. Liu, G. Hao, L. Zhang, K. Mao, X. Wang, D. Zhang, et al. 2017. Plastome
745 phylogeny and early diversification of Brassicaceae. *BMC Genomics* 18.
- 746 Hasegawa, M., H. Kishino, and T. Yano. 1985. Dating of the human-ape splitting by a
747 molecular clock of mitochondrial DNA. *Journal of molecular evolution* 22: 160–174.
- 748 Hernández Bermejo, J. E., and M. Clemente. 1993. *Lepidium* (L.) R. Br. *Flora iberica* 4:
749 311–327.
- 750 Jakobsson, M., and N. A. Rosenberg. 2007. CLUMPP: A cluster matching and permutation
751 program for dealing with label switching and multimodality in analysis of population
752 structure. *Bioinformatics* 23: 1801–1806.
- 753 Janes, J. K., J. M. Miller, J. R. Dupuis, R. M. Malenfant, J. C. Gorrell, C. I. Cullingham, and
754 R. L. Andrew. 2017. The K = 2 conundrum. *Molecular Ecology* 26: 3594–3602.
- 755 Jost, L. 2008. GST and its relatives do not measure differentiation. *Molecular Ecology* 17:
756 4015–4026.
- 757 Kamvar, Z. N., J. F. Tabima, and N. J. Grünwald. 2014. Poppr: an R package for genetic
758 analysis of populations with clonal, partially clonal, and/or sexual reproduction. *PeerJ* 2:
759 e281.

- 760 Karger, D. N., O. Conrad, J. Böhrer, T. Kawohl, H. Kreft, R. W. Soria-Auza, N. E.
761 Zimmermann, et al. 2017. Climatologies at high resolution for the earth's land surface
762 areas. *Scientific Data* 4: 1–20.
- 763 Larsson, A. 2014. AliView: a fast and lightweight alignment viewer and editor for large
764 datasets. *Bioinformatics* 30: 3276–3278.
- 765 Legendre, P., and L. F. J. Legendre. 2012. Numerical ecology. Elsevier.
- 766 Leigh, J. W., and D. Bryant. 2015. POPART: Full-feature software for haplotype network
767 construction. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 6: 1110–1116.
- 768 Manzano, P., and R. Casas. 2010. Past, present and future of Transhumancia in Spain:
769 Nomadism in a developed country. *Pastoralism: research, policy and practice* 1: 72–90.
- 770 Martínez-Nieto, M. I., M. Encarna Merlo, J. F. Mota, E. Salmerón-Sánchez, and J. G.
771 Segarra-Moragues. 2012. Microsatellite loci in the gypsophyte *Lepidium subulatum*
772 (Brassicaceae), and transferability to other Lepidieae. *International journal of molecular*
773 *sciences* 13: 11861–11869.
- 774 Matesanz, S., A. García-Fernández, A. Limón-Yelmo, A. Gómez-Fernández, and A.
775 Escudero. 2018. Comparative landscape genetics of gypsum specialists with naturally-
776 patchy distributions reveal their resilience to anthropogenic fragmentation. *Perspectives*
777 *in Plant Ecology, Evolution and Systematics* 34: 1–9.
- 778 Matesanz, S., M. Ramos-Muñoz, M. Blanco-Sánchez, A. García-Fernández, A. M. Sánchez,
779 and A. Escudero. 2019. Migración, variabilidad genética y plasticidad fenotípica en
780 especies de yesos y su papel en la respuesta al cambio climático. *Revista Ecosistemas* 28:
781 48–59.
- 782 Meirmans, P. G. 2006. Using the Amova Framework To Estimate a Standardized Genetic
783 Differentiation Measure. *Evolution* 60: 2399.
- 784 Meirmans, P. G. 2015. Seven common mistakes in population genetics and how to avoid
785 them. *Molecular Ecology* 24: 3223–3231.
- 786 Meyer, S. E. 1986. The ecology of gypsophile endemism in the eastern Mojave Desert.
787 *Ecology* 67: 1303–1313.
- 788 Miller, M. A., W. Pfeiffer, and T. Schwartz. 2010. Creating the CIPRES Science Gateway for
789 inference of large phylogenetic trees. *2010 Gateway Computing Environments*
790 *Workshop, GCE 2010*.
- 791 Moore, M. J., and R. K. Jansen. 2007. Origins and Biogeography of Gypsophily in the
792 Chihuahuan Desert Plant Group *Tiquilia* subg. *Eddya* (Boraginaceae). *Systematic Botany*
793 32: 392–414.
- 794 Mota, J. F., P. Sánchez-Gómez, and J. S. Guirado. 2011. Diversidad vegetal de las yeseras
795 ibéricas. *El reto de los archipiélagos edáficos para la biología de la conservación*.
796 *ADIF-Mediterráneo Asesores Consultores, Almería*.
- 797 Mummenhoff, K., A. Polster, A. Mühlhausen, and G. Theißen. 2009. *Lepidium* as a model
798 system for studying the evolution of fruit development in Brassicaceae. *Journal of*
799 *Experimental Botany* 60: 1503–1513.
- 800 Nei, M. 1987. Molecular evolutionary genetics. Columbia university press.
- 801 Nieto Feliner, G. 2014. Patterns and processes in plant phylogeography in the Mediterranean
802 Basin. A review. *Perspectives in Plant Ecology, Evolution and Systematics* 16: 265–278.
- 803 Oksanen, A. J., F. G. Blanchet, M. Friendly, R. Kindt, P. Legendre, D. Mcglinn, P. R.
804 Minchin, et al. 2019. Package ‘vegan’.
- 805 Van Oosterhout, C., W. F. Hutchinson, D. P. M. Wills, and P. Shipley. 2004. MICRO-
806 CHECKER: Software for identifying and correcting genotyping errors in microsatellite
807 data. *Molecular Ecology Notes* 4: 535–538.
- 808 Parsons, R. F. 1976. Gypsophily in plants-a review. *American Midland Naturalist*: 1–20.
- 809 Pérez-Collazos, E., P. Sánchez-Gómez, J. F. Jiménez, and P. Catalán. 2009. The

810 phylogeographical history of the Iberian steppe plant *Ferula loscosii* (Apiaceae): a test of
811 the abundant-centre hypothesis. *Molecular Ecology* 18: 848–861.

812 Petit, R. J., J. Duminil, S. Fineschi, A. Hampe, D. Salvini, and G. G. Vendramin. 2005.
813 Comparative organization of chloroplast, mitochondrial and nuclear diversity in plant
814 populations. *Molecular Ecology* 14: 689–701.

815 Pritchard, J. K., M. Stephens, and P. Donnelly. 2000. Inference of population structure using
816 multilocus genotype data. *Genetics* 155: 945–959.

817 Pueyo, Y., C. L. Alados, O. Barrantes, B. Komac, and M. Rietkerk. 2008. Differences in
818 gypsum plant communities associated with habitat fragmentation and livestock grazing.
819 *Ecological Applications* 18: 954–964.

820 R Core Team. 2018. R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation
821 for Statistical Computing. Austria: Vienna.

822 Rajakaruna, N. 2017. Lessons on Evolution from the Study of Edaphic Specialization.
823 *Botanical Review*: 1–40.

824 Rambaut, A., and A. J. Drummond. 2009. Tracer v1. 5.0.

825 Rambaut, A., and A. J. Drummond. 2014. TreeAnnotator v1. 8.2.

826 Romão, R. L., and A. Escudero. 2005. Gypsum physical soil crusts and the existence of
827 gypsophytes in semi-arid central Spain. *Plant Ecology* 181: 127–137.

828 Rosenberg, N. A. 2004. DISTRUCT: A program for the graphical display of population
829 structure. *Molecular Ecology Notes* 4: 137–138.

830 Rozas, J., A. Ferrer-Mata, J. C. Sánchez-DelBarrio, S. Guirao-Rico, P. Librado, S. E. Ramos-
831 Onsins, and A. Sánchez-Gracia. 2017. DnaSP 6: DNA Sequence Polymorphism Analysis
832 of Large Data Sets. *Molecular Biology and Evolution* 34: 3299–3302.

833 Santamaría, S., A. M. Sánchez, J. López-Angulo, C. Ormosa, I. Mola, and A. Escudero. 2018.
834 Landscape effects on pollination networks in Mediterranean gypsum islands. *Plant*
835 *Biology* 20: 184–194.

836 Schaal, B. A., D. A. Hayworth, K. M. M. Olsen, J. T. Rauscher, and W. A. Smith. 1998.
837 Phylogeographic studies in plants: problems and prospects. *Molecular Ecology* 7: 465–
838 474.

839 Stamatakis, A. 2014. RAxML version 8: a tool for phylogenetic analysis and post-analysis of
840 large phylogenies. *Bioinformatics* 30: 1312–1313.

841 Suc, J. P. 1984. Origin and evolution of the mediterranean vegetation and climate in Europe.
842 *Nature* 307: 429–432.

843 Suchard, M. A., P. Lemey, G. Baele, D. L. Ayres, A. J. Drummond, and A. Rambaut. 2018.
844 Bayesian phylogenetic and phylodynamic data integration using BEAST 1.10. *Virus*
845 *Evolution* 4: vey016.

846 Tajima, F. 1989. Statistical method for testing the neutral mutation hypothesis by DNA
847 polymorphism. *Genetics* 123: 585–595.

848 Terrab, A., P. Schönswetter, S. Talavera, E. Vela, and T. F. Stuessy. 2008. Range-wide
849 phylogeography of *Juniperus thurifera* L., a presumptive keystone species of western
850 Mediterranean vegetation during cold stages of the Pleistocene. *Molecular Phylogenetics*
851 *and Evolution*.

852 Thompson, J. D. 2005. Plant evolution in the Mediterranean. Oxford University Press on
853 Demand.

854 Verity, R., and R. A. Nichols. 2014. What is genetic differentiation, and how should we
855 measure it - G ST, D, neither or both? *Molecular Ecology* 23: 4216–4225.

856 Verity, R., and R. A. Nichols. 2016. Estimating the number of subpopulations (K) in
857 structured populations.

858 Wang, I. J. 2011. Choosing appropriate genetic markers and analytical methods for testing
859 landscape genetic hypotheses. *Molecular Ecology* 20: 2480–2482.

860 Weir, B. S., and W. G. Hill. 2002. Estimating F-Statistics. *Annual Review of Genetics* 36:
861 721–750.

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Table 1: Population code, location, geographical coordinates, elevation, and geographical region of the 27 populations of *Lepidium subulatum* L. used in this study.

Geographic region	Population code	Population location	Geographical coordinates		Altitude (m asl)	T. mean (°C)	T. min. (°C)	T. max. (°C)	Prec. (mm)
Duero Basin (DB)	BAL	Los Balbases (Burgos, Spain)	42° 13' 20.3" N	4° 4' 30.9" W	851	11.4	4.2	19.8	467.7
	PEÑ	Peñañiel (Valladolid, Spain)	41° 35' 25.0" N	4° 6' 30.1" W	815	12.6	4.5	22.0	432.3
	SEG	Valladolid (Segovia, Spain)	41° 24' 48.5" N	4° 25' 30.3" W	818	12.7	4.7	22.2	510.7
	TOR	Torquemada (Palencia, Spain)	42° 2' 26.6" N	4° 20' 49.3" W	833	12.1	4.6	20.8	443.6
Ebro Basin (EB)	ALF	Alfajarín (Zaragoza, Spain)	41° 37' 25.5" N	0° 41' 52.3" W	219	15.7	7.7	25.2	363.2
	GEL	Gelsa (Zaragoza, Spain)	41° 27' 5.3" N	0° 22' 24.6" W	254	15.7	7.6	25.3	367.3
	PER	Peralta (Navarra, Spain)	42° 23' 22.5" N	1° 48' 38.5" W	385	13.6	6.1	21.9	589.9
	TDL	Tamarite de Litera (Huesca, Spain)	41° 53' 9.5" N	0° 24' 58.5" E	418	13.8	6.0	23.0	490.0
	TER	Villalba Baja (Teruel, Spain)	40° 25' 9.7" N	1° 4' 48.2" W	954	12.0	4.2	21.5	339.7
Guadalquivir and Júcar-Segura Basins (GJSB)	AGR	Agramón (Albacete, Spain)	38° 24' 51.2" N	1° 37' 56.1" W	388	16.9	8.9	26.4	300.6
	APG	Altiplano granadino (Granada, Spain)	37° 33' 23.5" N	3° 2' 47.9" W	738	15.7	6.8	25.9	523.5
	BAZ	Hoya de Baza (Granada, Spain)	37° 38' 0.8" N	2° 34' 37.1" W	903	14.4	6.0	24.2	459.9
	CAB	Cabezo Redondo (Alicante, Spain)	38° 38' 32.9" N	0° 53' 33.5" W	533	15.7	8.2	24.4	370.7
	ECZ	Escúzar (Granada, Spain)	37° 3' 20.2" N	3° 44' 41.5" W	927	14.2	6.0	23.7	520.3
	TOP	Topares (Almería, Spain)	37° 52' 18.4" N	2° 11' 22.0" W	1157	12.4	4.4	21.9	395.1
	VAL	Valdeganga (Albacete, Spain)	39° 8' 10.4" N	1° 44' 26.7" W	632	15.2	7.1	25.1	346.7
	VY	Venta de Yesos (Almería, Spain)	37° 5' 2.3" N	2° 17' 7.3" W	539	16.3	9.4	24.7	254.7
Tajo Basin (TB)	ARA	Aranjuez (Madrid, Spain)	40° 1' 51.5" N	3° 32' 54.4" W	595	15.8	6.4	26.8	406.9
	AZQ	Aranzueque (Guadalajara, Spain)	40° 30' 23.7" N	3° 6' 47.1" W	742	13.6	5.3	24.2	414.9
	BEL	Belinchón (Cuenca, Spain)	40° 4' 43.5" N	3° 4' 3.7" W	706	15.1	5.8	26.0	419.2
	CHI	Chinchón (Madrid, Spain)	40° 10' 13.2" N	3° 25' 59.4" W	676	15.1	5.9	26.0	465.3
	PDG	Portalrubio de Guadamejud (Cuenca, Spain)	40° 16' 15.8" N	2° 35' 14.7" W	794	13.9	5.2	24.5	508.6
	SMV	San Martín de la Vega (Madrid, Spain)	40° 13' 19.2" N	3° 35' 3.3" W	551	15.6	6.4	26.6	376.3
	SPP	San Pedro Palmiches (Cuenca, Spain)	40° 25' 51.9" N	2° 23' 51.1" W	850	13.6	5.0	24.0	647.8
	YEB	Yebra (Guadalajara, Spain)	40° 20' 43.0" N	2° 56' 27.2" W	718	14.3	5.6	25.1	419.8
North Africa (NA)	ARGL	Chott Ech Chergui (Algeria)	34° 17' 59.3" N	0° 40' 33.5" E	989	16.4	6.8	27.9	257.3
	MAR	Yerada (Morocco)	34° 13' 29.4" N	2° 7' 21.2" W	944	16.5	8.1	26.5	282.2

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Table 2: Genetic diversity indices based on concatenated chloroplast *matK* and *psbA* regions for the 27 populations of *Lepidium subulatum*. Significant values for Tajima's *D*, Fu and Li's *F** and Fu's *F_S* tests are in bold.

Population code	N. of sequences	N. of segregating sites	N. of haplotypes	Haplotype diversity (Hd)	Nucleotide diversity (π)	Tajima's <i>D</i>	Fu and Li's <i>F*</i>	Fu's <i>F_S</i>
AGR	7	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
ALF	7	1	2	0.571	0.00080	1.342	1.102	0.856
APG	8	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
ARA	8	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
ARGL	2	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
AZQ	7	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
BAL	7	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
BAZ	7	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
BEL	8	2	2	0.250	0.00070	-1.310	-1.514	0.762
CAB	8	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
CHI	7	1	2	0.286	0.00040	-1.237	-1.374	0.856
ECZ	8	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
GEL	8	6	4	0.750	0.00334	0.215	0.881	0.869
MAR	10	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
PDG	8	3	3	0.607	0.00185	0.585	0.401	0.723
PEÑ	8	2	2	0.536	0.00150	1.449	1.297	2.083
PER	8	2	2	0.571	0.00160	1.794	1.384	2.216
SEG	8	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
SMV	8	3	2	0.571	0.00239	1.982	1.541	3.149
SPP	7	1	2	0.286	0.00040	-1.237	-1.374	0.856
TDL	8	1	2	0.250	0.00035	-1.310	-1.514	0.762
TER	8	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
TOP	7	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
TOR	8	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
VAL	8	0	1	0	0	-	-	-
VY	8	2	3	0.464	0.00070	-1.310	-1.514	-0.999
YEB	8	2	2	0.250	0.00070	-1.310	-1.514	0.762
Overall	204	19	22	0.747	0.00382	-0.399	-1.640	-5.931

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Table 3: Results of two different AMOVA tests for microsatellite and chloroplast markers: 1) non-hierarchical AMOVA; 2) hierarchical AMOVA considering the geographic location (regions) of the populations; df = degrees of freedom.

AMOVA type	Source of variation	Nuclear DNA					Chloroplast DNA				
		df	Sum of squares	Variance	Percentage of variation	p-value	df	Sum of squares	Variance	Percentage of variation	p-value
1) Non – hierarchical AMOVA	Among populations	25	1544.746	1.419	18.627 %	< 0.001	26	1389.277	6.129	46.080 %	< 0.001
	Within populations	982	6074.267	6.201	81.373 %		177	1269.484	7.172	53.920 %	
	Total	1007	7619.012	7.621	100 %		203	2658.760	13.302	100 %	
2) Populations grouped by geographic location	Among regions	4	368.845	0.227	2.955 %	< 0.001	4	831.532	4.691	32.815 %	< 0.001
	Among populations within regions	21	1175.901	1.245	16.230 %		22	557.745	2.432	17.015 %	
	Within populations	982	6074.267	6.201	80.815 %		177	1269.484	7.172	50.170 %	
	Total	1007	7619.012	7.673	100 %		203	2658.760	14.296	100 %	

870 **Table 4:** Genetic diversity indices of the 26 populations (excluding ARGL) of *Lepidium subulatum* using 10 microsatellite loci. *N*: Number of individuals
871 sampled; *N eff.*: Effective number of individuals sampled; *P*: percentage of polymorphic loci; *A*: Mean number of alleles per locus; *A_{rare}*: Rarefied number
872 of alleles per locus (10 individuals, 20 genes); *A_e*: Mean number of effective alleles per locus; *H_o*: Observed heterozygosity; *H_e*: Expected heterozygosity;
873 *F_{IS}*: Inbreeding coefficient; *β*: Population-specific *F_{ST}* coefficient.

Population code	<i>N</i>	<i>N eff.</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>A_{rare}</i>	<i>A_e</i>	<i>H_o</i>	<i>H_e</i>	<i>F_{IS}</i>	<i>β</i>	Nb. of private alleles	Nb. of genotypes
AGR	20	18.9	90.0%	3.8	3.47	2.54	0.528	0.548	0.060	0.245	0	20
ALF	20	19.7	100.0%	5.4	4.68	3.35	0.587	0.605	0.065	0.169	0	20
APG	20	19.9	100.0%	6.1	4.87	3.50	0.574	0.580	0.024	0.203	2	20
ARA	20	19.8	100.0%	5.9	4.91	3.29	0.621	0.618	-0.002	0.150	2	19
AZQ	20	19.9	100.0%	6.0	5.11	3.80	0.669	0.662	-0.009	0.090	2	20
BAL	20	19.5	100.0%	4.8	4.11	2.56	0.463	0.515	0.171	0.292	0	20
BAZ	20	19.8	100.0%	7.1	5.65	3.86	0.520	0.681	0.270	0.064	1	20
BEL	20	19.9	100.0%	7.0	5.57	3.89	0.538	0.647	0.178	0.111	1	20
CAB	20	19.6	100.0%	3.4	2.92	2.08	0.500	0.497	0.026	0.317	0	20
CHI	20	19.9	100.0%	6.8	5.54	3.71	0.557	0.627	0.111	0.138	1	20
ECZ	20	19.1	100.0%	4.5	3.76	2.32	0.470	0.505	0.074	0.306	0	20
GEL	20	19.9	100.0%	5.6	4.78	3.41	0.594	0.608	0.049	0.165	0	20
MAR	10	9.7	100.0%	4.5	4.50	3.05	0.479	0.602	0.258	0.149	1	10
PDG	20	19.6	100.0%	5.5	4.61	3.32	0.572	0.631	0.145	0.132	0	20
PEÑ	20	20	100.0%	6.0	5.10	3.53	0.570	0.667	0.144	0.084	1	20
PER	14	13.8	100.0%	4.0	3.79	2.79	0.718	0.601	-0.093	0.164	2	14
SEG	20	19.7	100.0%	3.3	3.01	1.93	0.471	0.452	0.000	0.379	0	20
SMV	20	19.3	90.0%	5.5	4.78	3.38	0.514	0.599	0.204	0.176	1	20
SPP	20	19.7	90.0%	4.1	3.49	2.49	0.415	0.483	0.153	0.335	1	19
TDL	20	20	100.0%	5.1	4.15	2.47	0.485	0.493	0.019	0.323	3	20
TER	20	19.5	100.0%	5.3	4.41	3.07	0.561	0.602	0.066	0.172	1	20
TOP	20	19.8	100.0%	4.8	4.17	2.89	0.548	0.594	0.134	0.184	0	20
TOR	20	20	100.0%	5.6	4.83	3.38	0.640	0.635	0.008	0.127	0	20
VAL	20	19.9	100.0%	4.4	4.03	3.14	0.663	0.619	-0.043	0.150	0	20
VY	20	19.8	100.0%	5.1	4.39	3.15	0.479	0.585	0.194	0.196	2	20
YEB	20	19.8	90.0%	4.2	3.75	2.64	0.479	0.521	0.094	0.283	2	20
Overall	504	19.096	98.5%	5.15	4.40	3.06	0.547	0.584	0.089	0.196	23	502

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875 **APPENDIX 1**

876 List of: a) GenBank accession numbers for ITS sequences used in this study (individuals with
 877 only one accession number included sequence for both ITS regions). b) GenBank accession
 878 numbers for *trnT-trnL*, *trnL* intron and *trnL-trnF* regions used in this study (hyphens indicate
 879 missing sequences).

880 a) *Arabidopsis arenicola*, GQ922906; *Arabidopsis arenosa* 1, AAU52182; *Arabidopsis arenosa* 2,
 881 AAU43231; *Arabidopsis arenosa* 3, AAU43230; *Arabidopsis arenosa* 4, AAU43232; *Arabidopsis arenosa*
 882 5, AAU43233; *Arabidopsis arenosa* 6, AAU43229; *Arabidopsis arenosa* 7, AAU52181; *Arabidopsis*
 883 *croatica* 1, DQ528930; *Arabidopsis croatica* 2, DQ528949; *Arabidopsis croatica* 3, DQ528826;
 884 *Arabidopsis croatica* 4, DQ528825; *Arabidopsis halleri* 1, DQ528887; *Arabidopsis halleri* 2, DQ528882;
 885 *Arabidopsis halleri* 3, DQ528881; *Arabidopsis halleri* 4, DQ528884; *Arabidopsis halleri* 5, DQ528883;
 886 *Arabidopsis halleri* 6, DQ528885; *Arabidopsis halleri* 7, DQ528886; *Arabidopsis lyrata* 1, DQ528819;
 887 *Arabidopsis lyrata* 2, DQ528815; *Arabidopsis lyrata* 3, DQ528820; *Arabidopsis lyrata* 4, DQ528814;
 888 *Arabidopsis lyrata* 5, DQ528817; *Arabidopsis lyrata* 6, DQ528816; *Arabidopsis lyrata* 7, DQ528821;
 889 *Arabidopsis lyrata* 8, DQ528818; *Arabidopsis pedemontana*, DQ914842; *Arabidopsis thaliana* 1,
 890 KM892649; *Arabidopsis thaliana* 2, DQ528813; *Cardaria chalepensis*, AJ628275, AJ628276; *Cardaria*
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 904 *Lepidium austrinum*, AJ582467, AJ582515; *Lepidium banksii* 1, AJ582433, AJ582490; *Lepidium banksii*
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 906 *bipinnatifidum*, AJ582446, AJ582522; *Lepidium biplicatum*, FM178550, FM178551; *Lepidium*
 907 *bonariense* 1, AJ582458, AJ582506; *Lepidium bonariense* 2, HM134831; *Lepidium campestre* 1,
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 909 *Lepidium capitatum*, FM178552, FM178553; *Lepidium cardamines* 1, FM178554, FM178555; *Lepidium*
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952 EF367919; *Lepidium montanum* 59, EF367920; *Lepidium muelleri ferdinandi*, AJ582427, AJ582484;
953 *Lepidium myriocarpum*, AJ582442, AJ582499; *Lepidium naufragorum* 1, AJ582422, AJ582479;
954 *Lepidium naufragorum* 2, AF100686; *Lepidium navasii* 1, KU213888; *Lepidium navasii* 2, KU213880;
955 *Lepidium navasii* 3, KU213881; *Lepidium navasii* 4, KU213882; *Lepidium navasii* 5, KM201470;
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1033 b) *Arabidopsis arenicola*, DQ914838, GQ244583, - ; *Arabidopsis croatica*, DQ529064, AY665580, - ;
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1035 *pedemontana*, KF547407, KF547039, - ; *Arabidopsis petrogena*, DQ529090, DQ313520, - ; *Arabidopsis*
1036 *suecica*, LN610047, AY167921, - ; *Arabidopsis suecica*, LN610047, AY167921, - ; *Arabidopsis thaliana*,
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 1061 AY015873, AY015767; *Lepidium oblongum*, AY015960, AY015874, AY015769; *Lepidium oleraceum*,
 1062 AY015961, AY015875, AY015771; *Lepidium oxycarpum*, AY015962, AY015876, AY015773; *Lepidium*
 1063 *oxytrichum*, AY015963, AY015877, AY015776; *Lepidium papillosum*, AY015964, AY015878,
 1064 AY015777; *Lepidium pedicellosum*, AY015965, AY015879, AY015779; *Lepidium perfoliatum*, KJ623396,
 1065 KJ623328, - ; *Lepidium phlebopetalum*, AY015966, AY015881, AY015783; *Lepidium pholidogynum*,
 1066 AY015967, AY015882, AY015785; *Lepidium pinnatifidum*, AY015968, AY015883, AY015787; *Lepidium*
 1067 *pinnatum*, AY015969, AY015884, AY015827; *Lepidium pseudohyssopifolium*, -, AY015885, AY015789;
 1068 *Lepidium pseudopapillosum*, AY015971, AY015886, - ; *Lepidium pseudotasmanicum*, AY015972,
 1069 AY015887, AY015826; *Lepidium quitense*, AY015973, AY015888, AY015794; *Lepidium rigidum*,
 1070 AY015974, AY015889, AY015828; *Lepidium ruderale*, KJ623452, KJ623383, AY015795; *Lepidium*
 1071 *schinzii*, AY015976, AY015892, AY015797; *Lepidium serra*, AY015977, AY015893, AY015799;
 1072 *Lepidium sisymbrioides*, DQ997054, -, - ; *Lepidium sisymbrioides subsp. kawarau*, AY015978, AY015894,
 1073 AY015801; *Lepidium sisymbrioides subsp. matau*, AY015979, AY015895, AY015803; *Lepidium*
 1074 *sisymbrioides subsp. sisymbrioides*, AY015980, AY015896, AY015805; *Lepidium spinescens*, AY015981,
 1075 AY015897, AY015807; *Lepidium spinosum*, AY015914, AY015898, AY015824; *Lepidium subulatum*, -
 1076 MW048753, MW048756; *Lepidium trifurcum*, AY015983, AY015900, AY015811; *Lepidium villarsii*,
 1077 AY015916, AY015901, AY015825.

1078 **Figure captions**

1079 **Figure 1:** a) Map of the Iberian Peninsula and North Africa showing all sampled populations
1080 and their assignment to regions for analyses of population structure (these regions are related
1081 to the main gypsum vegetation habitats described; Mota, Sánchez-Gómez, & Guirado, 2011);
1082 b), c) and d) Gypsum environments at ARA, SPP and TOP, respectively; e) Individual of
1083 *Lepidium subulatum* at the end of its fruiting period (mid-June); f) Flowers of *L. subulatum*.

1084

1085 **Figure 2:** Maximum clade credibility (MCC) tree obtained from the BEAST analysis based on
1086 concatenated *trnT-trnL*, *trnL* intron and *trnL-trnF* sequences. Blue bars show highest posterior
1087 densities (HPD) credibility intervals and numbers above branches show mean estimated
1088 divergence time (Mya). HPD and dates for *L. subulatum* are in bold and dark blue (Bayesian
1089 posterior probability of this node= 95%).

1090

1091 **Figure 3:** Haplotype network for 27 populations of *Lepidium subulatum*, based on concatenated
1092 *matK* and *psbA* sequences of 204 individuals. The main groups (A, B, C and D) are shown in
1093 the haplotype network. Three missing haplotypes (extinct or unsampled) are represented by
1094 small black dots in the haplotype network. The size of the different haplotypes in the network
1095 is proportional to the number of individuals with each haplotype. The size of the pie charts in
1096 the map is proportional to the number of samples in each population. Note that the location of
1097 the ARGL population is approximate. See Appendix S10 for haplotype networks for each locus.

1098

1099 **Figure 4:** Mantel Correlograms calculated from a) microsatellite and b) chloroplast markers.
1100 In both cases, solid squares indicate that the Mantel statistic is different from zero at the 95%

1101 confidence level. Distance classes were calculated using Sturge's rule (Legendre & Legendre,
1102 2012).

1103

1104 **Figure 5:** Population structure ($K=3$) inferred by Bayesian cluster analyses (STRUCTURE) for
1105 504 *L. subulatum* individuals from 26 populations. Each individual is represented by a vertical
1106 bar in each population. The size of the boxes is proportional to the number of individuals
1107 sampled in each population.

1108

1109 **Figure 1**

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1112 **Figure 2**

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1114 **Figure 3**

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1117 **Figure 4**

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1120 **Figure 5**

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